

Contents and proportions of endogenous brassinosteroids in maize subjected to water shortage depend on the state of the leaf/plantMarková H.^{1*}, Tarkowská D.², Čečetka P.¹, Kočová M.¹, Rothová O.¹, Holá D.¹¹ Department of Genetics and Microbiology, Faculty of Science, Charles University, Viničná 5, CZ-128 43 Prague, Czech Republic² Laboratory of Growth Regulators, Centre of the Region Haná for Biotechnological and Agricultural Research, Institute of Experimental Botany, Czech Academy of Sciences, v.v.i. and Palacký University, Šlechtitelů 27, CZ-78371 Olomouc, Czech Republic

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Supplementary Table 1 The changes in the contents of individual brassinosteroids (BRs) or their immediate precursors in the aboveground vegetative parts or roots of plants subjected to drought stress, together with the changes in some biochemical, physiological, morphological or developmental parameters characterizing the state of the experimental plants. The relative percentage of values determined in stressed plants to the values determined in non-stressed plants are presented. Full references are listed below. BL ... brassinolide, CS ... castasterone, DL ... dolicholide, DS ... dolichoesterone, TE ... teasterone, TY ... typhasterol. APX ... ascorbate peroxidase, CAT ... catalase, Car ... carotenoids, Chl ... chlorophylls, DM ... dry mass, E ... transpiration rate, Fm ... fresh mass, g_s ... stomatal conductance, MDA ... malondialdehyde, P_N ... net photosynthetic rate, POD ... peroxidase, RWC ... relative water content, SOD ... superoxide dismutase.

Experimental material / soil conditions (if stated)	Reported changes of BR contents / other parameters characterizing the state of plants due to drought stress	Reference
3 youngest fully developed leaves, 2 youngest internodes or apical bud of 35-d old pea plants Soil conditions not stated	CS 218%, 168% (<i>leaves, 9 d of drought, 2 independent experiments</i>), 121 % (<i>leaves, 14 d of drought</i>), 129% (<i>leaves, 14 d of drought</i>), 107% (<i>internodes, 14 d of drought</i>), 99% (<i>14 d of drought, apical bud</i>) Ratio of (FM-DM)/DM (<i>determined in the mixture of 7 leaves in slightly older plants</i>) 54%; leaf water potential (<i>determined in slightly younger plants</i>) 500%; plant height 77%; leaf length 74%; leaf width 71%, stem thickness 70%	Jager <i>et al.</i> 2008
Whole shoot of 14-d old rice plants Soil conditions not stated	CS 122% BL absent (present in non-stressed plants) No data on the plant state	Ding <i>et al.</i> 2014
Leaves of 14-d old barley plants Control plants = 70% soil field capacity; stressed plants = 25% soil field capacity; leaf wilting	CS 156% 24-epiBL present (absent in non-stressed plants) 28-homoCS 97% E 47%; g _s 25%; P _N 61%	Gruszka <i>et al.</i> 2016
Leaves of 52-d (stress) or 42-d (control) old tobacco plants Soil conditions not stated	CS 110% BL 97% RWC 62%; proline content 700%; MDA content 260%; H ₂ O ₂ content 229%; CAT activity 267%; SOD activity 61%; POD activity 128%; primary root length 109%; number of lateral roots 170% (<i>plants at the beginning of 10-d stress period taken as the non-stressed control</i>)	Duan <i>et al.</i> 2017

<p>Leaves of 28-d old Chinese cabbage, cabbage or kale plants</p> <p>Soil conditions not stated</p>	<p>TY 64% (<i>Chinese cabbage</i>), 97% (<i>cabbage</i>), 148% (<i>kale</i>) CS 157% (<i>Chinese cabbage</i>), 93% (<i>cabbage</i>), 80% (<i>kale</i>) BL 758% (<i>Chinese cabbage</i>), 80% (<i>cabbage</i>), 98% (<i>kale</i>)</p> <p>RWC of stressed plants approx. 45% (<i>control values not stated</i>); proline content 9200%, 390%, resp. 395%; MDA content 235%, 230%, resp. 235%; CAT activity 90%, 200%, resp. 52%; SOD activity 100%, 125%, resp. 130%; APX activity 150%, 175%, 110%; F_v/F_m 89%, 96%, resp. 100%; PI_{ABS} 44%, 44%, resp. 124% (<i>Chinese cabbage, cabbage and kale, respectively</i>)</p>	<p>Pavlovic <i>et al.</i> 2018</p>
<p>Fully developed 4th leaves of maize plants at the V5/V6 stage, 1 drought-tolerant and 1 susceptible cultivar</p> <p>Control plants = 20% soil water content; stressed plants = 3% soil water content</p>	<p>TY 120% (<i>tolerant cultivar</i>), 29% (<i>susceptible cultivar</i>) CS 100% (<i>tolerant cultivar</i>), 75% (<i>susceptible cultivar</i>) BL 100% (<i>tolerant cultivar</i>), 200% (<i>susceptible cultivar</i>) 28-norCS 67% (<i>tolerant cultivar</i>), 192% (<i>susceptible cultivar</i>) 28-norBL 48% (<i>tolerant cultivar</i>), 225% (<i>susceptible cultivar</i>) 28-homoCS 61% (<i>tolerant cultivar</i>), 88% (<i>susceptible cultivar</i>) 28-homoDS 89% (<i>tolerant cultivar</i>), 46% (<i>susceptible cultivar</i>)</p> <p>Leaf osmotic potential 225%, resp. 200%; E 77%, resp. 58%; g_s 75%, resp. 38%; P_N 55%, resp. 29%; Chl content 123%, resp. 87%; Car content 102%, resp. 89%; proline content 200%, resp. 200%; H₂O₂ content 103%, resp. 100%; membrane injury index 133%, resp. 150%; CAT activity 74%, resp. 162%; APX activity 51%, resp. 138%; shoot DM 103, resp. 67%; root DM 107, resp. 100%; plant height 115%, resp. 88%; total leaf area 85%, resp. 48% ; number of fully developed leaves 98, resp. 98% (<i>tolerant and susceptible cultivar, respectively</i>)</p>	<p>Tůmová <i>et al.</i> 2018</p>
<p>Leaves of barley plants at the heading stage; 3 drought-tolerant, 5 moderately tolerant and 2 susceptible cultivars</p> <p>Control plants = 75% soil water content; stressed plants = 35% soil water content (<i>probably meant soil field capacity!</i>)</p>	<p>TE 101%, 116%, 72% (<i>tolerant cultivars</i>), 106%, 98%, 75%, 103%, 92% (<i>moderately tolerant cultivars</i>), 160%, 172% (<i>susceptible cultivars</i>) CS 234%, 175%, 199% (<i>tolerant cultivars</i>), 100%, 146%, 107%, 173%, 143% (<i>moderately tolerant cultivars</i>), 94%, 104% (<i>susceptible cultivars</i>) DL 55%, 320%, 77% (<i>tolerant cultivars</i>), 88%, 110%, 91%, 153%, 217% (<i>moderately tolerant cultivars</i>), 386%, 50% (<i>susceptible cultivars</i>) 28-homoCS 79%, 259%, 70% (<i>tolerant cultivars</i>), 122%, 152%, 122%, 176%, 218% (<i>moderately tolerant cultivars</i>), 237%, 124% (<i>susceptible cultivars</i>)</p> <p>No data on the plant state</p>	<p>Malaga <i>et al.</i> 2020</p>
<p>8th leaves of tobacco plants</p> <p>Control plants = 80% soil field capacity; stressed plants = 60% soil field capacity</p>	<p>BL 48%</p> <p>Proline content 496%; soluble sugars content 154%; MDA content 178%; ROS content 153%; CAT activity 110%; SOD activity 55%; POD activity 242%</p>	<p>Khan <i>et al.</i> 2022</p>

<p>Whole shoot (without cotyledons) or roots of sunflower plants at the V2 stage, 2 cultivars</p> <p>Control plants = 60% soil field capacity; stressed plants = application of mannitol</p>	<p>TE 244% (<i>shoot, 1st cultivar</i>), 139% (<i>shoot, 2nd cultivar</i>), 54% (<i>roots, 1st cultivar</i>), 181% (<i>roots, 2nd cultivar</i>) CS 80% (<i>shoot, 1st cultivar</i>), 89% (<i>shoot, 2nd cultivar</i>), 125% (<i>roots, 1st cultivar</i>), 150% (<i>roots, 2nd cultivar</i>) BL 85% (<i>shoot, 1st cultivar</i>), absent (present in non-stressed plants) (<i>shoot, 2nd cultivar; roots, 1st cultivar</i>), absent in both stressed and non-stressed plants (<i>roots, 2nd cultivar</i>) 24-epiBL 100% (<i>shoot, 1st cultivar</i>), 111% (<i>shoot, 2nd cultivar</i>), 160% (<i>roots, 1st cultivar</i>), 100% (<i>roots, 2nd cultivar</i>) 28-homoCS 72% (<i>shoot, 1st cultivar</i>), 7% (<i>shoot, 2nd cultivar</i>), 100% (<i>roots, 1st cultivar</i>), 9% (<i>roots, 2nd cultivar</i>)</p> <p>Shoot osmotic potential 82%, resp. 90%; root osmotic potential 71%, resp. 89%; g_s 37%, resp. 66%; shoot carbohydrate content 700%, resp. 460%; root carbohydrate content 400%, resp. 350%; shoot DM 47%, resp. 55%; root DM 60%, resp. 100%; leaf area 60%, resp. 68%; plant height 103%, resp. 74%; root length 63%, resp. 71%</p>	<p>Boero <i>et al.</i> 2023</p>
<p>Leaves of 2-years old plants of grapewine</p> <p>Stressed plants = application of PEG</p>	<p>CS 92% (<i>0.5 d of drought</i>), 98% (<i>1 d of drought</i>), 50% (<i>2 d of drought</i>), 89% (<i>3 d of drought</i>), 76% (<i>4 d of drought</i>) BL 171% (<i>0.5 d of drought</i>), 169% (<i>1 d of drought</i>), 138% (<i>2 d of drought</i>), 115% (<i>3 d of drought</i>), 200% (<i>4 d of drought</i>)</p> <p>No data on the plant state</p>	<p>Cui <i>et al.</i> 2023</p>
<p>Older (3rd) or younger (4th) leaves and roots of 54-d old maize plants; drought susceptible cultivar</p> <p>Control plants = 22% soil water content; stressed plants = 9.3 % soil water content</p>	<p>TY 175% (<i>older leaf</i>), 50% (<i>younger leaf</i>), 75% (<i>roots</i>) CS 12% (<i>older leaf</i>), 48% (<i>younger leaf</i>), 79% (<i>roots</i>) BL 133% (<i>older leaf</i>), 31% (<i>younger leaf</i>), 75% (<i>roots</i>) 24-epiBL 56% (<i>older leaf</i>), absent in both stressed and non-stressed plants (<i>younger leaf</i>), 100% (<i>roots</i>) 28-norCS 101% (<i>older leaf</i>), 199% (<i>younger leaf</i>), 133% (<i>roots</i>) 28-norBL 55% (<i>older leaf</i>), absent in both stressed and non-stressed plants (<i>younger leaf</i>), 79% (<i>roots</i>) 28-homoCS 69% (<i>older leaf</i>), 30% (<i>younger leaf</i>), 71% (<i>roots</i>) 28-homoDS 40% (<i>older leaf</i>), 47% (<i>younger leaf</i>), 51% (<i>roots</i>)</p> <p>Leaf RWC 83%, resp. 95%; E 36%, resp. 44%; g_s 33%, resp. 39%; P_N 40%, resp. 38%; Chl content 65%, resp. 63%; Car content 82%, resp. 77%; F_v/F_m 87%, resp. 89%; PI_{ABS} 40%, resp. 47%; proline content 557%, resp. 1011%; MDA content 274%, resp. 76%; membrane injury index 157%, resp. 152% (<i>older and younger leaf, respectively</i>); shoot DM 63%; root DM 88%; plant height 72%; number of fully developed leaves 85%</p>	<p>Marková <i>et al.</i> 2023</p>
<p>Leaves of 25-d old wheat plants</p> <p>Control plants = 72% soil water content (<i>probably meant soil field capacity!</i>); stressed plants = not stated</p>	<p>24-epiCS 417% 24-epiBL 344% 28-norTE 154% 28-norCS 513% 28-norBL 146% 28-homoCS 166%</p> <p>Data on the plant state given for a completely different cultivar</p>	<p>Nisler <i>et al.</i> 2023</p>

Roots of rice plants in PMC meiosis telophase stage	24-epiBL 143% 28-homoBL 137%	Zhang <i>et al.</i> 2023
Control plants = soil saturated with water; stressed plants = soil water potential -10 to -15 kPa	E 98%; g _s 97%; P _N 97%; leaf osmolality 114%; root oxidation activity 127%; root active absorption area 143%; root xylem sap flow rate 88%	
Crowns of barley plants at tillering stage, 2 cultivars, two sampling times	CT 113% (<i>day 3 of drought, cultivar 1</i>), 129% (<i>day 10 of drought, cultivar 1</i>), 67% (<i>day 3 of drought, cultivar 2</i>), 62% (<i>day 10 of drought, cultivar 2</i>) CS 80% (<i>day 3 of drought, cultivar 1</i>), 117% (<i>day 10 of drought, cultivar 1</i>), 304% (<i>day 3 of drought, cultivar 2</i>), 110% (<i>day 10 of drought, cultivar 2</i>) BL 57% (<i>day 3 of drought, cultivar 1</i>), 158% (<i>day 10 of drought, cultivar 1</i>), 106% (<i>day 3 of drought, cultivar 2</i>), 38% (<i>day 10 of drought, cultivar 2</i>)	Kuczynska <i>et al.</i> 2024
Control plants = more than 70% soil field capacity; stressed plants = 20% soil field capacity	No data on physiological state of plants given; only data associated with yield parameters	

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